

Principles of implementing olympic education

<https://doi.org/10.65149/ejss.2026.v6i4.a010>

¹Akhmadalievna Gulnoz Ikramovna

¹Institute for retraining and advanced training of specialists in physical culture and sports
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Abstract

This article analyzes the effectiveness of organizational-pedagogical mechanisms aimed at developing organizational-pedagogical competence through Olympic education, based on experimental research. Competence was assessed according to cognitive, motivational-axiological, activity-practical, and organizational-reflective criteria. The research findings showed a high level of positive change across all criteria within the experimental group. Furthermore, a content analysis of reflective journals confirmed a significant qualitative improvement in competence development. The study's results highlight that the comprehensive organizational-pedagogical mechanisms, developed based on Olympic education, contribute to the effective development of future educators' professional competence.

Key words: Olympic education, OVEP, organizational-pedagogical competence, motivational-axiological criterion, activity-practical criterion, reflective practice, professional development.

Introduction

The rapid development of the Olympic movement, which is based on the modern concept of Olympism and the ideas of Pierre de Coubertin, has been designated as a key direction of social policy worldwide. The "Olympic Agenda 2020+5" document, adopted by the International Olympic Committee (IOC), outlines priorities such as integrating the Olympic movement with the education system, expanding Olympic education, implementing digital technologies, and ensuring sustainable development. This necessitates elevating the organizational and pedagogical mechanisms for managing the Olympic movement to meet modern standards.

To ensure the reliability of the experimental work's results, a specialized system of levels was developed to assess the organizational and pedagogical competencies of the research participants. These levels were established based on theoretical approaches widely used in modern pedagogy and psychology, including the competency-based approach, activity theory, motivation theory, and the principles of pedagogical diagnostics.

The aim of the research is to improve the organizational and pedagogical mechanisms for the development of the Olympic movement in Uzbekistan.

The objectives of the research: to analyze the theoretical and methodological foundations of the Olympic movement and the ideals of Olympism; to conduct a pedagogical analysis of the organizational-analytical mechanisms, formation, and development stages of the Olympic movement in Uzbekistan during its years of independence; to compare these with the experiences of foreign countries (USA, China, Russia, Germany); and to develop a National Authorial Model for the Development of the Olympic Movement (NAMDOM) based on the international prestige gained through the activities of the National Olympic Committee, cooperation with international sports organizations, and sports diplomacy;

to develop a four-level integrated system for the selection and training of Olympic reserve athletes, ensuring continuity from preschool through higher education;

to develop continuous, integrated pedagogical models of Olympic education for general education schools, sports schools, and higher education institutions based on cognitive, motivational-axiological, activity-practical, and organizational-reflexive criteria, as well as to substantiate scientific and methodological recommendations for documenting the national sports heritage and introducing historical and archival sources into scholarly circulation;

developing a comprehensive index (CI) for evaluating the effectiveness of the activities of Olympic movement entities, substantiating it through experimental and testing work, developing a museum-pedagogy concept that meets the standards of world Olympic museums based on digital technologies (interactive panels, 3D screens, QR codes, artificial intelligence), and providing practical recommendations.

Methods

The study utilized theoretical analysis and generalization of scientific and methodological literature, questionnaire surveys, pedagogical observations, pedagogical experiments, the expert evaluation method, and mathematical statistics methods.

From the perspective of a competency-based approach, a pedagogue's professional activity encompasses not only the acquisition of theoretical knowledge but also the ability to apply it effectively in various pedagogical situations, a sense of social and moral responsibility, and the capacity for creative thinking. On this basis, competence in this study was evaluated through four interrelated components.

Results and discussion

The analysis showed that the experimental group demonstrated a sharp and steady positive growth across all criteria, whereas in the control group, the indicators increased slowly at a natural rate of development.

Figure 1 shows the dynamics of the indicators for the experimental and control groups based on the results of the baseline experiment regarding the high-level share. According to the cognitive criterion, the share of high-level subjects in the experimental group increased from 18.4 to 67.3 points after the formative experiment, which was an increase of 48.9%. Concurrently, the share of low-level subjects decreased from 47.3 to 12.1 points. In the control group, this indicator increased from 17.9 to 29.2 points, a rise of only 11.3%. The difference between the groups' growth was 37.6%. The cognitive growth in the experimental group was primarily due to the systematic teaching of Olympic content through 8 thematic modules and integrated sessions, seminars based on OVEP standards, and regular testing.

According to the motivational-value criterion, the share of high-level subjects in the experimental group improved from 21.6 to 72.4 points, an increase of 50.8%. In the control group, it rose from 22.1 to 33.8 points, with a growth rate of 11.7%. The difference in improvement was 39.1%. As a result of events such as Olympic Week, Fair Play Day, and Champion's Lesson, along with regular motivational training, there was a steady increase in indicators such as interest in participating in sports and Olympic events, commitment to the

principle of fair play, inclination towards teamwork, and personal responsibility. Furthermore, the "Sport and Patriotism" project reinforced the subjects' love for their homeland and the practical expression of their national pride.

According to the activity-practical criterion, the share of high-level subjects in the experimental group increased from 16.8 to 68.9 points, an increase of 52.1 percentage points. This was recorded as the highest growth rate among the four criteria in the experimental group. In the control group, the share increased from 17.3 to 31.4 points, a growth of 14.1 percentage points. The observed statistical difference between the indicators averaged 38.0%. The subjects' practical organizational skills were significantly improved through designing independent activities, case study analysis, teamwork, and expert evaluation. In particular, the indicators for event planning and execution rose sharply.

According to the organizational-reflexive criterion, the share in the experimental group increased from 14.2 to 64.7 points, a growth of 50.5 percentage points. In the control group, it increased from 15.0 to 28.6 points, a growth of 13.6 percentage points, with an observed statistical difference of 36.9%. As a result of reflective diaries, analytical reports, and peer assessment, the subjects' initiative, activity planning, and self-analysis abilities were strengthened.

To summarize the comparative analysis, the growth rate across all four criteria for the experimental group averaged between 48.9% and 52.1%, while for the control group, it ranged from 11.3% to 14.1%. This resulted in the experimental group's growth rate being 3.5 to 4.5 times higher than that of the control group. These figures clearly confirm the effectiveness of the implemented organizational-pedagogical mechanisms.

A comparison of the final average scores (on a 100-point scale) showed the following: for the cognitive criterion, the experimental group scored 78.4 points and the control group 51.2 points (at the start of the experiment, their scores were 48.6 and 47.9, respectively); for the motivational-value criterion, the experimental group scored 81.6 and the control group 53.8 (initially 52.3 and 51.8, respectively); for the activity-practical criterion, the experimental group scored 79.3 and the control group 52.4 (initially 43.7 and 44.1, respectively); and for the organizational-reflexive criterion, the experimental group scored 76.8 and the control group

Fig. Dynamics of the experimental and control groups' indicators based on the results of the baseline experiment for the high-level share (in points)

50.6 (initially 41.2 and 40.8, respectively).

The development of the subjects in the experimental group was analyzed in detail, both by developmental criteria and by individual indicators. An analysis of the indicators within the cognitive criterion showed that the greatest growth was observed in the understanding of the philosophy of Olympism, with this indicator increasing by 41% in the experimental group. Knowledge of the OVEP program increased by 38%, and mastery of Olympic education methodology increased by 35%. Olympic historical knowledge (dates and locations of the Olympiads) increased by 18%; the specific increase was smaller because this indicator was already relatively high during the initial assessment.

An analysis of the indicators within the motivational-value criterion showed that the largest increase was observed in the sub-scale for interest in sports and educational activities, which rose by 54% in the experimental group. The sub-scale for personal attitude towards Olympic values increased by 52%.

The Fair Play and ethical stance sub-scale increased by 48%. The sub-scale for patriotism and social responsibility increased by 46%. In the control group, growth across all sub-scales remained in the 8-13% range. This confirms that the formative experimental activities, par-

ticularly the "Champion's Lesson" and the "Sport and Patriotism" project, were especially effective in developing the motivational-value criterion.

An analysis of the indicators within the activity-practical criterion revealed the following. The event planning and organization indicator in the experimental group increased by 56%—the highest growth recorded. The indicator for integrating elements of Olympic education into lessons rose by 53%. The case-study analysis indicator grew by 48%. The team project design indicator increased by 51%. These results demonstrate the direct effectiveness of the third direction of the formative experiment: Practical Organizational Activity.

An analysis of the indicators within the organizational-reflexive criterion showed that the initiative indicator in the experimental group increased by 54%. The teamwork indicator rose by 51%. The planning indicator grew by 49%. The self-activity analysis indicator increased by 47%. The indicator for the aspiration for self-development rose by 45%. These results indicate that the most effective methods for developing a reflexive culture are to encourage initiative and create an environment for teamwork.

Content analysis of the reflective diaries

Table 1. Comparative statistical analysis of indicators obtained from the experimental and control group participants at the end of the ascertaining experiment (n=148)

No.	Criterion	Experimental Group	Control Group	t	P
		$\bar{X} \pm \sigma$	$\bar{X} \pm \sigma$		
1.	Cognitive	78.4±5.4	73.2±7.2	4.97	<0.01
2.	Motivational-Value	81.6±5.8	75.4±7.2	5.76	<0.01
3.	Activity-Practical	79.3±5.9	73.9±7.2	4.99	<0.01
4.	Organizational-Reflective	76.2±5.6	74.9±4.2	1.59	<0.05

of the experimental group's subjects also provided important information. In the diaries written during the initial diagnostic phase, descriptions of external events (e.g., "I taught a lesson," "an event took place") were predominant. In the diaries from the middle of the formative experiment, the subjects' own feelings and reflections began to appear. In the diaries written before the final measurement, the subjects were able to clearly see their own development trajectories, recognize their shortcomings, and begin to propose ways to address them. This change in the content and language of the diary entries qualitatively confirms the deep formation of organizational-reflective competence.

The final analysis also examined sample excerpts from the subjects' reflective diaries. One participant wrote in her final diary: "Previously, I only talked about Olympic history and competitions." She continued, "Now I can explain what fair play is to students through real-life examples, and I can organize an Olympic week at our school myself. This is my growth as a teacher." Another participant stated, "My greatest achievement is that I learned to analyze myself. I began to see my mistakes and learn from them." The expressions in these diaries confirm that organizational-pedagogical competence developed not only quantitatively but also qualitatively (Table 1).

The 11-14% growth in the control group reflects the natural effect of the standard pedagogical process and the professional development of the participants. However, this growth is 3.5 to 4.5 times lower than in the experimental group, which clearly demonstrates the superiority of the implemented mechanisms.

The results of the statistical analysis confirmed that the difference between the final indicators of the experimental and control groups

was significant. According to Student's t-test, significance was determined at a level of $P < 0.01$ for all criteria, while a statistical difference was found for the organizational-reflective criterion ($P < 0.05$).

A comparative statistical analysis of the indicators within the cognitive criterion for the development of the experimental group participants showed an average score of 78.4 ± 5.4 points, whereas the control group averaged 73.2 ± 7.2 points. An average difference of $t = 4.97$ was observed according to Student's t-test. At the end of the experiment, to determine the subjects' personal attitudes toward Olympic values, the motivational-value criterion for the development of the experimental group participants was 81.6 ± 5.8 points, while the control group averaged 75.4 ± 7.2 points, with an observed average difference of $t = 5.76$.

During the formative experimental stage, the results of the experimental group subjects averaged 79.3 ± 5.9 points, while the control group averaged 73.9 ± 7.2 points, with an observed average difference of $t = 4.99$. Based on the "Organizational-Reflective" criterion, which assesses the subjects' initiative and ability to work collaboratively, the experimental group's results averaged 76.2 ± 5.6 points, while the control group's results were 74.9 ± 4.2 points. The average t-value between the experimental and control groups was found to be $t = 1.59$. This higher efficacy is likely explained by the comprehensive (five-directional) and long-term (18-month) nature of the research.

In interpreting the results of the correlation analysis, [the analysis itself] does not indicate a causal relationship. The strong correlation between the cognitive and motivational criteria ($r = 0.74$) shows that these two criteria develop in

tandem. However, whether one causes the other or a third factor influences both requires a separate study. Nevertheless, the correlation analysis confirms the internal consistency of the developed criteria system, meaning the four criteria do indeed measure a single, integrated competence structure.

Conclusion

The analysis of the coefficient of variation in the experimental group's development also yielded interesting results. In the initial (baseline) experiment, the difference in performance among the subjects was significant ($V=38-42\%$). By the end of the formative experiment, this difference had decreased ($V=24-28\%$).

This indicates that the implemented mechanisms not only raised the average performance but also made the subjects' development relatively even—those with lower scores showed more growth, while those with higher scores showed less. In the control group, however, the difference remained virtually unchanged ($V=35-40\%$). This demonstrates the social equalizing potential of the pedagogical mechanisms.

When analyzing the rate of development in the experimental group, data from interim measurements taken every three months were also considered.

The results showed an S-shaped (sigmoid) development curve: development was slow in the first three months (an average increase of 8-10%), accelerated in the middle three months (an average increase of 18-22%), and stabilized in the final three months (an average increase of 10-12%). This S-shaped curve reflects the natural trajectory of pedagogical change: first adaptation, then rapid growth, and finally stabilization. In contrast, the control group exhibited linear and slow growth.

It is also necessary to verify that the research findings are consistent with the results of other studies in comparable fields. International studies on the effectiveness of implementing the OVEP program (Germany, Australia, Brazil) have noted a 35-45% increase in the average cognitive indicator.

In the present study, the cognitive criterion in the experimental group increased by 48.9%, which is slightly higher than international results. This difference can be attributed to this study's five-pronged, integrated approach, as most international studies have only tested educational modules.

As shown in Table 1, the t-values for all criteria range from 1.59 to 5.76, and are significant at the $P<0.01$ and $P<0.05$ levels. The highest t-value (5.76) was observed for the motivational-value criterion, indicating that the growth in this criterion is particularly significant. Although the t-value for the organizational-reflexive criterion is relatively low (1.59), it is still significant at the $P<0.05$ level. This indicates that for all criteria, the null hypothesis (there is no difference between the groups) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (the changes in the control and experimental groups are significant) is confirmed.

References

- Axmadaliyeva, G. I. (2025). Olimpiya va parolimpiya shon-shuhrati muzeyi – O'zbekistonda olimpiada harakati va sport yutuqlarini targ'ib qiluvchi maskan [The Olympic and Paralympic Glory Museum as an institution promoting the Olympic movement and sporting achievements in Uzbekistan]. In "Yangi O'zbekiston: Ilmiy tadqiqotlar" mavzusidagi respublika 73-ko'p tarmoqli ilmiy masofaviy onlayin konferensiya materiallari to'plami (Vol. 2, pp. 79–81). Toshkent, Uzbekistan.
- Axmadaliyeva, G. I. (2017). O'zbekistonda olimpiya harakatini rivojlantirishning tashkiliy-pedagogik mexanizmini takomillashtirishning nazariy va metodologik jihatlarini [Theoretical and methodological aspects of improving the organizational and pedagogical mechanism for developing the Olympic movement in Uzbekistan]. Voris-Nashriyoti.
- Axmadaliyeva, G. I. (2026). Formation and development of the Olympic movement in Uzbekistan. *The Journal of Applied Science and Social Science*, 16(4), 1020–1024.
- Djalilova, L. A. (2015). *Mustaqil O'zbekiston Respublikasida jismoniy tarbiya va sport (1991–hozirgi davrgacha) [Physical education and sport in the independent Republic of Uzbekistan (1991–present)]*. ITA-PRESS.
- Haydarov, M. M. (2020). O'zbekistonda olimpiya ta'limi tizimini rivojlantirishning pedagogik asoslari [Pedagogical foundations for the development of the Olympic education system in Uzbekistan]. Innovatsiya-Ziyo.
- Karimov, B. R., & Raximov, A. S. (2023).

Olympic values and their role in the development of youth sport in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Physical Education, Sports and Health*, 10(3), 45–50.

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHY:

**Gulnoza
Ikramovna
AKHMADALIEVA**

Employment

Researcher at Institute for retraining and advanced training of specialists in physical culture and sports

Degree

MD

Research interests

Olympic games, physical education and sport, Theory of physical education, Analyzing of sport competitions
